

What is a data management plan?

A data management plan (DMP) is a document which outlines the strategy, procedure, and tools that will be used to handle research data throughout the data life cycle. A meaningful DMP goes beyond the minimum requirements of research funding organizations, and puts focus on the research data as the main outcomes of the research process.

Why write a DMP?

A DMP is not just a way to tick boxes on a funding application! It is a tool to improve the research process and outcomes. The primary purpose of a DMP is to ensure that data is properly described, documented, acquired at high quality standards, stored, and archived in a way that ensures long-term accessibility and usability by the wider research community.

Who is this guide for?

Anyone involved in scientific research should be aware of data management practices including how to prepare a good data management plan. Our guide can help anyone who is approaching a data management plan and is looking for advice on the content, how to realise data management goals or where to find useful resources.

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This flyer contains excerpts from the FAIRmat guide to writing research data management plans. Visit our website to read the full guide.

QUICK GUIDE

Research Data Management Plans

Responsibilities and resources

Highly effective teams have clearly assigned roles, responsibilities and resources. Outline all the tasks involved in implementing your DMP and make sure they are clearly assigned to appropriately qualified people. Determine whether additional funding is needed e.g. to hire a new staff member.

Data exchange and long-term accessibility

The project has ended, long live the data! This is the plan for the data after the project has ended. It includes data preservation (how, where and for how long the data will be stored) and dissemination (how, where and when data will be accessible).

Legal obligations and conditions

Do it right: legally and ethically! Make sure that you are aware of legal issues around data storage and sharing, and account for them in your DMP. These include ownership, intellectual property, copyright and licensing laws.

Data description

Know what you need to manage! Before you start, it is important to know the nature and scope of your data. Your data description should cover the data's type, source, format and volume.

Documentation and data quality

Create a record of all the workflows for generating, structuring, and analyzing research data. To ensure that your data is organized, easily searchable, and of high quality, you'll need to develop a strategy for managing it effectively. Make sure to organize your data well, include rich metadata, perform quality control and document everything.

Storage and technical archiving

For the love of data, keep what you hold in your heart safe and secure! Ensure that your data is stored in a way that is both secure and accessible. Include a backup procedure for digital data and don't forget about physical data such as samples.

